

Do Flood Damage Cost Models Predict Real Losses for Residential Buildings? - Empirical Benchmarking from Denmark and Its Implications for Climate Adaptation Appraisal

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Abstract

Flood damage cost models are widely used to evaluate the benefits of climate adaptation investments, yet their predictive performance is seldom tested against observed losses. This paper presents the first empirical validation of the three official Danish flood damage models—Oversvømmelsesloven, SkadesØkonomi, and Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen—using observed insurance payouts from major storm surge and cloudburst events affecting residential buildings between 2010 and 2017.

Drawing on nationally comprehensive claims data from the Danish storm surge compensation scheme and private cloudburst insurance records, we assess model accuracy, bias, and explanatory power using a range of standard validation metrics. The results reveal substantial and systematic overestimation of flood damages across both hazard types: predicted losses typically exceed realized payouts by factors of two to five, none of the models outperforms a simple mean-based benchmark, and out-of-sample coefficients of determination are consistently negative. Increased model complexity does not translate into improved predictive performance.

To place these findings in an international context, we review the empirical validation evidence for widely used flood damage models, including HAZUS-MH, BN-FLEMOps, the Rhine Atlas model, and the JRC global model. The Danish results mirror a broader pattern of limited predictive accuracy documented internationally, suggesting a systemic challenge in contemporary flood damage modelling rather than a country-specific shortcoming. These findings imply that cost–benefit analyses of flood protection investments may substantially overstate expected benefits when based on existing damage models. We therefore argue that routine empirical validation, transparent model documentation, and minimum per-

formance standards should become integral components of climate adaptation appraisal.

Keywords: Flood damage modelling, Cost–benefit analysis, Climate adaptation, Model validation, Insurance loss data, Depth–damage functions, Empirical benchmarking, Denmark

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1 Introduction

Flooding is among the costliest natural hazards globally, and its economic burden is projected to grow due to climate change. In Europe, this increase is driven by several reinforcing factors: rising sea levels, more frequent storm surges, more intense precipitation, and continued urban development in flood-exposed areas. Together, these trends are expected to increase annual flood damages by an order of magnitude under high-emission scenarios (Alferi et al., 2018; IPCC, 2022). In response, governments have expanded investment in flood protection and climate adaptation on a scale demanding rigorous economic justification. Central to allocation of funds are flood damage cost models, which translate physical hazards into monetary loss estimates and provide the primary empirical input to CBAs of adaptation measures. The economic case for any investment rests on the quality of those estimates: if they are inaccurate, the apparent benefits of protection are distorted, and resources may be allocated inefficiently.

In standard CBA, the expected annual damage avoided by a protective measure constitutes its principal benefit, discounted over the investment horizon against construction and maintenance costs. This calculus is highly sensitive to damage assumptions: moderate changes in estimated losses can reverse investment recommendations, shift the socially optimal level of protection, or alter the ranking of strategies (Aerts et al., 2018; Kind, 2014). Systematic bias affects regulatory thresholds, insurance pricing, and adaptation budgets. Overestimation inflates apparent returns and can justify inefficient investment, whereas underestimation leaves communities exposed. As Pindyck (2017) emphasizes, precise looking but poorly calibrated estimates can be more misleading than transparent acknowledgment of uncertainty, providing a false sense of rigor that discourages scrutiny.

Despite their central role in adaptation policy, flood damage models are only infrequently validated against the realized losses they aim to predict. The large, methodologically diverse literature ranges from statistical models fitted to post-event insurance records to engineering frameworks that assign damage fractions to building components without systematic reference to observed outcomes (Gerl, Kreibich, Franco, Marechal, & Schröter, 2016; Merz, Kreibich, Schwarze, & Thieken, 2010). Where empirical benchmarking has been conducted, the findings point to important limitations: standard depth–damage functions explain only a modest share of observed household-level losses, different models applied to the same event can yield substantially divergent estimates, and simple empirical benchmarks sometimes perform comparably to or better than complex official models (Jongman et al., 2012; Kreibich, Seifert, Merz, & Thieken, 2010; Schröter et al., 2014; D. J. Wagenaar, de Bruijn, Bouwer, & de Moel, 2016).

This pattern is not confined to Europe. Drawing on 13.5 million U.S. flood insurance claims, Porter et al. (2023) show that depth–damage functions estimated directly from claims reproduce observed payouts reasonably well, even as they diverge substantially from the curves embedded in the federal HAZUS framework. This suggests that the gap between official model outputs and re-

alized losses reflects how those curves were constructed, not any inherent limit on empirically grounded functions.

Part of this validation gap reflects a research-practice disconnect: high-quality micro-level loss data are often held by insurance companies as commercially sensitive, so much of the literature relies on stylized assumptions, small post-event surveys, or reconstructed damage estimates. As a result, flood adaptation appraisal remains only partially anchored in systematically observed loss outcomes.

This paper uses Denmark as a data-rich institutional case to examine whether flood damage models predict realized losses. Denmark is particularly well suited for such a validation exercise: flood damage models are formally embedded in climate adaptation appraisal, and comprehensive insurance claims data provide an unusually strong empirical benchmark against which model predictions can be assessed. The country is exposed both to coastal storm surges along its North Sea and Baltic coastlines and to intense pluvial flooding in urban areas. In response to these risks, Denmark has institutionalized three nationally endorsed flood damage models: Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen, Oversvømmelsesloven, and SkadesØkonomi described in Section 3. Their outputs inform investment decisions, regulatory designations, and municipal planning choices involving substantial resources.

Despite this institutional prominence, to our knowledge, none of the three models has been systematically and rigorously benchmarked against realized flood losses. Although unit cost estimates based on insurance payouts from a major cloudburst event were published in 2014 (COWI, 2014), the underlying derivation was insufficiently documented, limiting transparency, reproducibility, and external validation. We address this gap by comparing model-based event-level damage estimates for residential buildings with observed insurance payouts from major storm surge and cloudburst events between 2010 and 2017. Storm surge compensation flows through a mandatory national pool - Stormrådet - covering all Danish house owners, while cloudburst damages are documented through private insurance claims. Together, these provide an unusually comprehensive benchmark that directly mirrors the models' policy applications.

For each claim type, we assess performance using five standard error metrics—Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Absolute Difference (AD), Average Absolute Difference (AAD), and Coefficient of Determination (COD). The model-calculated damages are evaluated against observed insurance payouts, with the mean observed payout used as a naïve benchmark for predictive performance.

The results show a consistent pattern. Across both hazard types and the full range of event magnitudes examined, all three models systematically overestimate residential flood damages, typically by factors of two to five. Across the analyses, the models perform worse than a simple benchmark that predicts damages using the mean observed insurance payout. Increased model complexity does not mitigate this problem: the most elaborate model, SkadesØkonomi, performs no better than the simpler regulatory models. These findings are consistent with a body of international evidence showing that official flood damage

models are often insufficiently validated against realized losses. In the Danish case, limited documentation makes it difficult to determine what damage concept the models are intended to approximate, while the empirical results show that they do not predict observed payouts well. Their uncritical use in CBA may therefore inflate the estimated benefits of flood protection.

The paper makes three contributions. First, it provides an empirical validation of officially endorsed flood damage models in a data-rich national setting. Denmark is particularly well suited for this purpose because comprehensive insurance records allow model predictions to be benchmarked against observed losses. This offers evidence on a validation problem that is difficult to examine in many countries because comparable loss data are rarely available. Second, it situates the Danish evidence within the international validation literature, showing that the weaknesses identified are not country-specific but reflect broader challenges in how flood damage models are developed, documented, and applied. Third, it contributes to wider debates in environmental and resource economics on the credibility of quantitative models in policy appraisal. When officially endorsed models perform worse than simple empirical benchmarks, their apparent precision may provide limited policy value unless supported by transparent documentation, empirical validation, and clear standards for use in cost–benefit analysis.

The remainder of the paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 reviews the international literature against four scientific criteria: transparency, reproducibility, empirical validation, and methodological robustness. Section 3 describes the three Danish models and their institutional roles. Section 4 outlines the benchmarking methodology and performance metrics. Section 5 presents the data and event selection. Section 6 reports the empirical results for storm surge and cloudburst events. Section 7 discusses implications for flood risk modelling and adaptation policy, and Section 8 concludes.

2 Review of Residential Flood Damage Models: Approaches and Scientific Credibility

This section reviews leading international residential flood damage models to assess whether the validation gap identified in the Danish case reflects a broader problem in flood damage modelling. The review uses four criteria that constitute the scientific standards a damage model must meet for credible policy appraisal: transparency (assumptions and methods documented sufficiently for scrutiny); reproducibility (functions constructible from accessible data and disclosed procedures); empirical validation (predictions tested against realized losses from independent events); and methodological robustness (sound statistical procedures either uncertainty appropriately characterized). These criteria correspond closely to the informational requirements of credible CBA: a model failing transparency cannot be audited and one lacking validation offers little assurance that its predictions correspond to realized losses. The review focuses

on the four models identified by Goyal and Mukherjee (2025) as the principal empirically informed residential flood damage tools: HAZUS-MH in the United States, BN-FLEMOps in Germany, the ICPR/Rhine Atlas model for the international Rhine basin, and the JRC global model for the European Union. This selection is deliberately conservative: these models represent the subset of used tools that meet at least a minimal empirical-information criterion, while other damage models rely on synthetic, engineering-based assumptions.

2.1 HAZUS-MH (United States)

HAZUS-MH is the federally mandated U.S. flood loss framework. Its residential depth–damage functions were derived from National Flood Insurance Program (NFIP) claims combined with U.S. Army Corps of Engineers engineering curves, through an undisclosed credibility-weighting procedure (FEMA, 2022; National Research Council, 2015). Transparency is therefore limited, neither the model form, sample sizes per depth class, nor weighting parameters are documented sufficiently for replication, and reproducibility is low since the NFIP database is non-public, and the official curves cannot be reconstructed from available materials. Empirical validation studies reflect these limitations. Fitting fully specified statistical models to large NFIP datasets, Wing, Pinter, Bates, and Kousky (2020) use over two million claims to demonstrate that residential damages follow highly variable, often bimodal distributions incompatible with the deterministic, monotonic HAZUS-MH curves. Porter et al. (2023) derive pluvial depth–damage functions based on US data that differ markedly from the federal standard. Taken together, this evidence indicates that the HAZUS-MH curves depend on modelling choices that are not sufficiently documented. External validation studies raise concerns about their predictive performance, but the undocumented derivation of the official curves makes it difficult to identify which modelling assumptions drive these discrepancies.

2.2 BN-FLEMOps (Germany)

BN-FLEMOps provides a benchmark against which other models can be judged. It is a probabilistic Bayesian network model predicting probability distributions of relative building loss conditional on inundation depth, duration, building type, precautionary measures, and prior flood experience, with parameters estimated by maximum likelihood from household-level post-event survey data in the HOWAS21 database (Lüdtke et al., 2019; D. Wagenaar, Lüdtke, Schröter, Bouwer, & Kreibich, 2018). Transparency is high: structure, variables, and estimation procedures are documented in peer-reviewed publications. Reproducibility is partial, since HOWAS21 requires a formal access application (Kreibich, Thielen, Haubrock, & Schröter, 2017). Crucially, BN-FLEMOps stands apart from the other reviewed models because its development and validation are documented in a way that allows the model to be scientifically assessed. Its median loss estimates outperformed an ensemble of models for the 2002 Mulde flood, and reported losses from major floods in Germany, Austria, and Italy fall within

its 95% credibility intervals (Lüdtke et al., 2019; Steinhausen, Schröter, Wagenaar, Lüdtke, & Kreibich, 2020). BN-FLEMOps demonstrates that statistically grounded, validated residential flood damage modelling is feasible. So the other models' limitations reflect institutional choices rather than inherent constraints.

2.3 ICPR / Rhine Atlas (international river basin district Rhine)

The Rhine Atlas model, now implemented in the ICPR's FloRiAn GIS tool, applies relative damage fractions to six aggregated land-use categories from Corine Land Cover data (ICPR, 2001; Schröter et al., 2018). Its functions were derived from HOWAS21, but aggregating building-level observations into six broad classes removes much of the heterogeneity that the data provides. Thus, the model is empirically informed but synthetic in application. Transparency is partial—the general methodology is documented in ICPR technical reports, but the statistical aggregation procedures are not specified in sufficient detail for replication—and formal validation against independent event-level loss data is limited. Comparative analyses applying multiple European models to identical flood scenarios find Rhine Atlas predictions diverging from those of other models by factors of two to five, with no ground-truth anchor to determine which estimates are closest to realized losses (de Moel & Aerts, 2011; Jongman et al., 2012).

2.4 JRC Global Flood Depth–Damage Functions (European Union)

The JRC global depth–damage database (Huizinga, de Moel, & Szewczyk, 2017) provides continent-level fractional damage functions for use in pan-European and global flood risk assessments. Curve shapes are synthesized from existing national depth–damage functions and maximum damages are calibrated to national construction cost data. Transparency and reproducibility are comparatively high: the methodology is public and the database openly accessible. In contrast, empirical validation is absent. As the curves were synthesized rather than fitted to observed losses, they inherit and propagate the errors of the source models. Huizinga et al. (2017) acknowledge this explicitly, describing the functions as first-order approximations for regional analysis rather than validated predictors of local event losses. Analyzing specific European events, comparative studies find large discrepancies relative to national models and observed outcomes (Dottori et al., 2017; Jongman et al., 2012).

2.5 Synthesis: A Structural Validation Gap

With the exception of BN-FLEMOps, the principal international models reviewed here provide limited transparency on how empirical evidence is translated into operational damage functions. Several models draw on observed loss data or empirically derived curves, but their estimation procedures, weighting

choices, aggregation steps, or calibration assumptions are insufficiently documented. This makes their empirical basis difficult to reproduce, evaluate, or diagnose. In addition, most have not undergone rigorous out-of-sample validation; where such validation has been conducted, studies often identify systematic biases and limited explanatory power (Kreibich et al., 2010; Porter et al., 2023; Schröter et al., 2014; D. J. Wagenaar et al., 2016). Table 1 summarizes the assessment across all four criteria.

This is not primarily a data problem: large insurance claims datasets exist in several countries and properly analyzed, yield robust estimates diverging substantially from official model outputs (Porter et al., 2023; Wing et al., 2020). The main constraint is institutional rather than technical - models are often developed in response to regulatory demand for deployable decision tools rather than scientific validation standards. The practical consequence is that CBAs of flood protection investment often rest on damage estimates whose relationship to expected realized losses is empirically unestablished.

Table 1: Assessment of international residential flood-damage models against four scientific criteria.

Model	Transparency	Reproducibility	Empirical validation
HAZUS-MH (USA)	Low	Low	Low
BN-FLEMOps (Germany)	High	Partial	High
ICPR / Rhine Atlas (Rhine basin)	Partial	Partial	Low
JRC Global Model (EU)	High	High	Low

“

Note: High = criterion is substantively met; Partial = criterion is partially met with notable gaps; Low = criterion is not meaningfully met; Unassessable = insufficient documentation to evaluate.

3 Flood Damage Modelling in Denmark: Institutional Context and Model Specifications

Denmark’s three official flood damage models are described in the following section. They share the predominant characteristics of the international landscape: limited transparency, restricted reproducibility, and an absence of empirical validation. What distinguishes the Danish context is the availability of nationally standardized insurance claims data that make validation possible. To date, however, such validation has not been undertaken.

3.1 Flood Exposure and the Policy Context

Denmark faces significant and growing exposure to both coastal and pluvial flooding. With over 7,000 km of coastline and extensive low-lying areas, it is vulnerable to storm surges affecting many properties in a single event. Simultaneously, Danish cities—characterized by aging combined sewer systems and high impervious surface coverage—are vulnerable to short, high-intensity rainfall events that overwhelm drainage (Danish Meteorological Institute, 2013; Stormrådet, 2018). Both hazards are projected to intensify under sea-level rise and more extreme rainfall (Olesen et al., 2014).

Danish adaptation policy has been shaped by two major events: the July 2011 Copenhagen cloudburst (insured losses over DKK 6 billion (approximately EUR 800 million)), which catalyzed a restructuring of municipal obligations for urban water management, and the December 2013 storm surge, driven by the extratropical cyclone Bodil, which inundated coastal properties nationwide and remains the dominant event in our storm surge insurance. Subsequent events, including storm surges Egon (2015) and Urd (2016), confirmed that coastal flood risk is neither stable nor declining. In response, Danish authorities have institutionalized quantitative flood damage models in adaptation governance: municipalities must develop climate adaptation plans including quantified flood-risk assessments, and national investment decisions rest on formal CBAs.

All three Danish models, despite different institutional origins and scopes, translate physical flood characteristics into monetary loss estimates through standardized assumptions about exposed buildings, property values, and vulnerability. However, they differ in how flood intensity is represented. The storm surge models rely on inundation depth, while the cloudburst models do not; instead, they are based mainly on inundated building area and standardized unit damages. None has been validated against observed Danish flood losses. Only *Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen* appears to have been developed as an attempt to base damage values on observed loss experience, but that derivation is neither publicly documented nor reproducible (Brøndum, Jørgensen, & Ladefoged, 2022). As Section 2 documents, this places them within the dominant international pattern: institutionally embedded, widely applied, but empirically unverified. The following subsections describe each model’s functional form, inputs, and institutional role.

3.2 *Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen* (Danish Environmental Protection Agency)

Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen is a cloudburst-specific model developed by COWI for the Danish Environmental Protection Agency to support municipal decision-making on urban water management service levels, providing standardized cost estimates to evaluate alternative protection levels for cloudburst drainage infrastructure. The model is limited to single-family houses and row houses, excluding apartments, commercial properties, and public infrastructure, which is an important constraint in dense urban settings such as Copenhagen, where

multi-storey housing constitutes a substantial share of exposure.

The model expresses expected flood losses as a function of the flooded area of a building, distinguishing between above-ground living space and basement. For flooded living space, the damage function takes the form:

$$D_{\text{living}} = \alpha \cdot A_{\text{living}} \quad (1)$$

where D_{living} is the estimated monetary damage to above-ground living area (DKK), A_{living} is the inundated floor area of the living space (m^2), and α is a standardized unit damage value (DKK/ m^2) specified in the national damage value tables (Miljøstyrelsen, 2025). For flooded basement space, an analogous linear relationship applies:

$$D_{\text{basement}} = \beta \cdot A_{\text{basement}} \quad (2)$$

where D_{basement} is the estimated damage to the basement (DKK), A_{basement} is the inundated basement floor area (m^2), and β is the corresponding unit damage value for basement flooding. Total building damage is the sum of equations (1) and (2). The unit damage values α and β are specified in national standard tables, updated periodically, and expressed in fixed DKK terms. Critically, there is no publicly available documentation explaining how these unit values were derived (Arnbjerg-Nielsen, Panduro, Andersen, Asmussen, & Nielsen, 2022), and prior work has shown that they cannot be reproduced using available data from the events that appear to have motivated them (Brøndum et al., 2022). On the four criteria set out in Section 2, the model’s parameters are not publicly documented, its derivation has not been reproduced from available data, and its statistical basis therefore cannot be assessed externally.

3.3 Oversvømmelsesloven (Danish Coastal Authority)

Oversvømmelsesloven was developed by the Danish Coastal Authority under the transposition of the EU Floods Directive into Danish law. It is the primary tool for coastal flood risk assessment, designating risk zones, appraising coastal protection, and determining eligibility for state-subsidized flood defense. The model covers permanent residential buildings and vacation homes but excludes apartment buildings and commercial properties. Unlike Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen, Oversvømmelsesloven links damage directly to inundation depth, making it sensitive to the assumed water level at each property.

Building damage is modelled as a depth-dependent fraction of the building’s actual value, V_{building} , calculated as the difference between the total property value and the land value, both assessed by the Danish tax authorities (Kystdirektoratet, 2021). The damage function for structural building losses is:

$$D_{\text{building}} = f(h) \cdot V_{\text{building}} \quad (3)$$

where D_{building} is the estimated structural damage (DKK), h is the inundation depth (m), V_{building} is the building replacement value (DKK), and $f(h)$ is

a depth–damage fraction that increases with h . The function $f(h)$ is specified identically for permanent residential buildings and vacation homes, reflecting an assumption that vulnerability to structural damage is independent of property use. In addition to structural damage, the model includes separate terms for damage to household contents. For permanent residences:

$$D_{\text{contents,residential}} = g(h) \cdot V_{\text{contents}} \quad (4)$$

and for vacation homes:

$$D_{\text{contents,vacation}} = g'(h) \cdot V'_{\text{contents}} \quad (5)$$

where $g(h)$ and $g'(h)$ are depth-dependent content damage fractions and $V_{\text{contents}}, V'_{\text{contents}}$ are standardized content values for each property type. Total event damage per property is the sum of equations (3), (4), and (5) where applicable. As with Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen, the Coastal Authority provides no documentation of how the depth–damage fractions $f(h)$, $g(h)$, or $g'(h)$ are derived (Arnbjerg-Nielsen et al., 2022), making it impossible to evaluate their empirical basis, reproducibility, or statistical soundness. Predictions are highly sensitive to inundation depth, since the damage fraction is a nonlinear function of h , so small variations in assumed water levels can produce large changes in estimated total losses—a sensitivity we exploit in the benchmarking by running all analyses under both high and low-water scenarios.

3.4 SkadesØkonomi (DTU Management)

SkadesØkonomi, developed by DTU Management, is the most comprehensive of the three models. Designed as a full welfare-economic framework for evaluating adaptation strategies, it encompasses residential, commercial, and infrastructure damage and feeds directly into CBAs for scenario analysis across a range of hazard intensities (Halsnæs, Dømggaard, Larsen, & Skougaard Kaspersen, 2021). It has been used in prominent national assessments, including analyses of major coastal protection investments (EY, 2024). Its greater complexity raises an important question addressed in this paper: whether more elaborate methodology translates into improved predictive accuracy.

For coastal storm surge events, SkadesØkonomi employs a natural logarithm specification that captures a diminishing marginal damage rate with increasing depth. The rationale is that the most critical damage to a building occurs when water first enters—affecting floors, electrical systems, and household contents—while additional depth causes proportionally less incremental damage. For residential properties and vacation homes, structural damage is specified as:

$$D_{\text{residential}} = \gamma_r \cdot \ln(h) \cdot V_{\text{building}} \quad (6)$$

$$D_{\text{vacation}} = \gamma_v \cdot \ln(h) \cdot V_{\text{building}} \quad (7)$$

where γ_r and γ_v are model-specific scaling parameters for residential and vacation properties respectively, h is inundation depth, and V_{building} is the replacement value of the structure. The model additionally incorporates separate damage terms for basements (D_{basement}) and attached garages (D_{garage}), each specified as functions of depth and the replacement value of the relevant building component (Halsnæs et al., 2021). Total storm surge damage per property is the sum of all applicable terms.

For cloudburst events, SkadesØkonomi adopts the same area-based structure as Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen, linking losses to the inundated floor area of basements and above-ground living spaces. It extends that framework by modelling vacation homes separately and by adding a dedicated garage damage term (Halsnæs, Kaspersen, Mik-Meyer, & Sunding, 2024):

$$D_{\text{cloudburst}} = \alpha' \cdot A_{\text{living}} + \beta' \cdot A_{\text{basement}} + \delta \cdot A_{\text{garage}} \quad (8)$$

where α' , β' , and δ are unit damage values for living space, basement, and garage respectively, and A denotes the relevant inundated floor area (m^2).

4 Benchmarking Methodology

4.1 Design Rationale and Identification Strategy

The central challenge in evaluating flood damage models is identifying a credible empirical benchmark. An ideal benchmark would capture the full economic cost of each flood event at the property level, disaggregated by building type and hazard characteristic, and recorded consistently across events and geographic areas. In practice, such comprehensive records are rarely available. The common alternatives—post-event household surveys and engineering damage assessments, are episodic, inconsistently collected, and subject to documented reporting biases (Merz et al., 2010; Meyer et al., 2013), while catastrophe-model outputs, sometimes used as pseudo-benchmarks, are themselves model-dependent and therefore unsuitable for independent validation.

The Danish institutional context mitigates this challenge. As noted above, storm surge compensation is administered through Stormrådet, a mandatory national insurance pool in which all property insurers participate. So, every eligible claim is processed through a single channel, generating nationally standardized payout records free of voluntary-market selection biases. Cloudburst compensation flows through private building and contents insurance, covering most residential properties. Together the two sources provide a comprehensive and consistent record of event-level insurance payouts.

Using these insurance payouts as the benchmark requires three clarifications. First, payouts represent compensated rather than total economic losses excluding uninsured damages, sub-deductible damages, and indirect losses. Thus, the observed payouts constitute a conservative lower bound. A model that modestly overpredicts may be capturing real economic damage that the claims data do not record. We interpret small positive bias charitably, as potentially reflecting

coverage of uncompensated losses; whether the observed bias is small enough for this interpretation to hold is an empirical question addressed in Section 6. Second, the three Danish models are designed to estimate damages to insured residential buildings—precisely the benchmark’s scope. Third, insurance data are a well-established validation benchmark in the literature (Kreibich et al., 2010; Schröter et al., 2014; Wing et al., 2020) and does not require stronger assumptions than alternative benchmarks.

4.2 Benchmarking Procedure

The benchmarking proceeds in two steps. First, event-level damage estimates are computed for model by applying the respective damage functions - as specified in Section 3 - to the property-level data described in Section 5. For each flooded parcel, the relevant hazard input (inundated area or depth) and property characteristics (floor area, basement area, building replacement value, property type, presence of a garage) are used to calculate property-level damage estimates which are then aggregated to the event level. For the two depth-based models (Oversvømmelsesloven and SkadesØkonomi), damage estimates are computed under both a high and a low-water level scenario for each storm surge event to account for uncertainty in the local inundation depth.

In the second step, event-level model predictions P_i are compared against the corresponding observed insurance payouts O_i using the five performance metrics defined in Section 4.3 below. All monetary values are expressed in 2023 DKK to ensure comparability across events spanning 2010 to 2017. The analysis is conducted separately for the two hazard types - coastal storm surges and urban cloudbursts - and, where data permit, disaggregated by building category: single-family houses, vacation homes, and apartments. This disaggregation is analytically important because the three models differ in their property coverage, and systematic performance differences across building categories can reveal whether observed biases are linked to model scope rather than to the damage functions per se.

4.3 Performance Metrics

Model performance is assessed using five metrics that together provide a multi-dimensional view of predictive accuracy, aggregate bias, and explanatory power. Let O_i denote the observed insurance payout for event i , P_i the corresponding model prediction, \bar{O} the sample mean of observed payouts, and n the number of events in the relevant sample. The five metrics are defined in Table 2 and described below.

Table 2: Performance metrics used in the benchmarking exercise.

Metric	Formula	Dimension	Interpretation
MAE	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n O_i - P_i $	DKK	Average absolute prediction error per event; scale-dependent measure of accuracy.
RMSE	$\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - P_i)^2}$	DKK	Root mean squared error; penalizes large individual errors more heavily than MAE.
AD	$\sum_{i=1}^n O_i - \sum_{i=1}^n P_i$	DKK	Aggregate bias across all events; positive values indicate systematic overestimation of total losses.
AAD	$\frac{1}{n} \times \sum_{i=1}^n O_i - \sum_{i=1}^n P_i $	DKK	Average signed deviation per event; distinguishes direction of bias from its magnitude.
COD	$1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - P_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})^2}$	Dimensionless	Proportion of observed variance explained. Negative values indicate the model performs worse than predicting the sample mean for all events.

Note: O_i = observed insurance payout for event i ; P_i = model prediction for event i ; \bar{O} = sample mean of observed payouts; n = number of events.

MAE and RMSE are the primary measures of predictive accuracy. Both are expressed in DKK and therefore scale with event magnitude. RMSE assigns greater weight to large individual errors by squaring deviations before averaging. AD and AAD capture aggregate and per-event signed bias respectively: positive values indicate overprediction, while negative values indicate underprediction. Unlike MAE and RMSE, these directional metrics can mask offsetting errors - a model that alternately over- and underpredicts by equal amounts would register a small AD despite large individual deviations. We therefore report all five metrics together rather than relying on any single statistic.

The COD statistic - defined here as the proportion of observed variance explained by the model relative to the variance explained by the sample mean - plays a central role in the analysis. In standard regression settings, COD is bounded between 0 and 1 by construction. In a prediction context, however, where model predictions are not fitted to the observed sample but rather applied out-of-sample, COD can take negative values. A negative COD indicates that the model's predictions are on average further from realized outcomes than the sample mean of past losses. In other words, a decision-maker simply using the historical average would have made smaller errors than one relying on the official model. We treat this as a minimum standard of practical relevance: a model that does not outperform this naïve baseline provides little additional information, beyond historical experience, for predicting event-level losses.

4.4 The Naïve Baseline and the Standard of Practical Relevance

A recurring finding in the validation literature is that complex flood damage models frequently fail to outperform simple empirical benchmarks (Schröter et al., 2014; D. J. Wagenaar et al., 2016). This observation has direct implications for the economics of information: if a sophisticated model is not more accurate than extrapolating from historical averages, its added complexity incurs costs without additional benefits as development and application require data collection, technical expertise, and institutional maintenance and may crowd-out simpler, more transparent tools.

Throughout, model performance is evaluated both in absolute terms—how close predictions match observed outcomes—and relative to a naïve baseline of predicting each event’s cost using the in-sample mean of observed payouts across all other events in the relevant hazard category. A model is considered to have practical policy relevance only if it outperforms this baseline on COD. Where it does not, its point estimates should enter CBA only with explicit calibration or an uncertainty allowance.

This establishes a minimum credibility standard rather than endorsing the historical average as a satisfactory policy tool.

5 Data

5.1 Insurance Claims Data

The empirical benchmark consists of insurance payout records for major coastal storm surge and urban cloudburst events between 2010 and 2017. The two hazard types are administered through distinct institutional channels with different coverage characteristics, described below.

Storm surge compensation is channeled through Stormrådet, the Danish Storm Council, which administers a mandatory national reinsurance pool under the Storm Surge Act. All property insurers operating in Denmark must participate and claims formally declared storm surge events are processed through this single administrative system. Its mandatory and universal character matters for the validity of the insurance benchmark. First, coverage is effectively complete for insured residential properties: there is no adverse selection or market fragmentation. Second, a standardized claim processing protocol produces records that are comparable across insurers and events. The storm surge dataset was obtained directly from Stormrådet and provides event-level payouts disaggregated by property type (permanent residences and vacation homes) and by building component (structure and contents).

For cloudbursts, compensation flows through standard building and contents policies issued by private insurers, which typically cover sewer backup and surface water flooding. The claims data used here were originally compiled by Insurance & Pension Denmark (Forsikring & Pension) from its member companies before the introduction of the GDPR regime and were subsequently used

among practitioners to support local flood-risk assessment and model validation. Given the high penetration of household insurance in Denmark, these records provide a broadly representative benchmark for compensated residential cloudburst losses. At the same time, access to such data has become more restricted under GDPR-related legal uncertainty. This illustrates a wider institutional challenge for flood damage model validation: the data needed to evaluate model performance often exist, but their use for research and applied risk management depends on clear legal frameworks for secure data sharing. The cloudburst dataset provides event-level payouts disaggregated by building category (single-family houses, apartments, and where available, vacation homes) and damage component. All values are converted to 2023 DKK using the Danish consumer price index.

The benchmark’s principal limitation is that it captures compensated losses rather than the full economic cost of flooding. Damages that fall below the household deductible, losses to uninsured properties, damage to public infrastructure, and indirect economic costs - including displacement, lost income, and psychological harm - are not reflected in the payouts. For the purpose of this study, this matters less than in other contexts because the three models being evaluated are each designed to estimate damages to insured residential buildings precisely the scope that the insurance data capture. Therefore, the comparison is internally consistent. Moreover, since insurance payouts represent a lower bound on true losses, a model that substantially overpredicts cannot defend its predictions on the grounds that uncompensated losses make up the difference.

5.2 Event Selection

The study covers all events with sufficient insurance claims for a meaningful comparison. For storm surge events, we apply a minimum threshold of 40 claims per event. Below this threshold, event-level averages risk being driven by idiosyncratic individual claims rather than the systematic relationship between flood characteristics and losses. Thus, the threshold excludes smaller, less severe events, which may limit generalizability to low-intensity, high-frequency flooding - a limitation we revisit in the discussion.

Table 3 lists all included and excluded events. The storm surge sample comprises four events: Bodil (December 2013), Egon (January 2015), Urd (December 2016), and an unnamed surge in January 2017. Bodil is the dominant event in terms of both geographic extent and claim volume. The remaining three events provide within-sample variation in magnitude for assessing performance across the severity distribution. For Urd, West Coast tide gauge readings are excluded because no insured losses were reported there. The cloudburst sample spans multiple events between 2010 and 2017, dominated by the July 2011 Copenhagen cloudburst. No minimum threshold is applied to cloudburst events given the uniformly high claim volumes.

Table 3: Overview of flood events and insurance claim observations.

Storm floods		Cloudburst	
Events	No. Observations	Events	No. Observations
06-12-2013/Bodil	1778	14-08-2010	7687
10-01-2015/Egon	46	02-07-2011	29658
29-11-2015	3 (not included)	14-08-2011	165
27-12-2016/Urd	58	26-08-2011	483
05-01-2017/Jan2017	154	29-06-2012	153
29-10-2017	21 (not included)	06-08-2012	483
		26-08-2013	403
		23-05-2014	952
		30-08-2014	2924
		16-10-2014	270

Note: Observation counts refer to individual insured properties with recorded claims. Storm surge events excluded on the basis of the minimum claims threshold are aggregated in the final storm surge row.

5.3 Water Depth Measurement for Storm Surge Events

Oversvømmelsesloven and SkadesØkonomi both require inundation depth as their primary hazard input. In the absence of event-specific hydrodynamic modelling at the property level, we construct a depth proxy using sea level measurements from the Danish national tide-gauge network (Poulsen, Grupe, Frank, Piontkowitz, & Bonde, 2024). For each event, the inundation depth at a property is approximated as the recorded sea level elevation minus the building’s ground elevation above the national vertical datum (DVR90), from the national digital elevation model.

This approximation involves an important source of uncertainty that requires explicit treatment. Storm surges are dynamic phenomena: water levels rise, peak, and recede at different times across the inundated area, and the maximum recorded level at a coastal gauge may not represent conditions at a specific property, especially inland or in sheltered locations. Furthermore, gauge readings represent point measurements at fixed stations and must be interpolated to characterize conditions across a spatially heterogeneous coastline. Using a single peak level as the depth input therefore introduces measurement error that could bias damage predictions in either direction.

To bound this uncertainty, all calculations for the two depth-based models apply two scenarios per storm surge event: a high scenario (maximum recorded water level at the nearest tide gauge) and a low scenario (second-highest reading). The resulting depth pairs (Table 4 range from 7 cm for January 2017 to 167 cm for Urd, providing a meaningful sensitivity range given the nonlinear relationship between depth and predicted damage in both models. Running both scenarios’ tests whether the directional findings—systematic overestimation, poor explanatory power—are robust to plausible variation in the depth input.

Table 4: Recorded sea level elevations used in high and low-water depth scenarios for storm surge events.

Event	Date	High scenario (cm, DVR90)	Low scenario (cm, DVR90)
Bodil	Dec 2013	206	181
Egon	Jan 2015	225	164
Urd	Dec 2016	326	159
January 2017	Jan 2017	177	170

Note: Water levels expressed in centimeters above the Danish national vertical datum (DVR90). High scenario uses the maximum recorded gauge reading for the event; low scenario uses the second-highest reading. Source: Poulsen et al. (2024).

5.4 Property-Level Variables

All three models require a small set of property-level inputs. For each flooded parcel in the dataset, the following variables are specified: (i) the inundated floor area of above-ground living space (m^2); (ii) the inundated basement floor area (m^2), where applicable; (iii) a binary indicator for property type (permanent residence or vacation home); (iv) a binary indicator for the presence of an attached or detached garage; and (v) the building replacement value (DKK), calculated as the difference between total assessed property value and land value, both obtained from the Danish tax authority’s property registers in accordance with the valuation rules specified in the Coastal Authority’s methodology (Kystdirektoratet, 2021). No variables beyond those required by the models are introduced, ensuring the benchmarking exercise evaluates the models as actually applied in policy contexts, rather than in an idealized augmented version.

For cloudburst events, the treatment of apartment buildings requires a modelling assumption. Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen attributes cloudburst damage in apartments to basement flooding only. Because basement area in multi-unit buildings is recorded at building level rather than individual unit level, we approximate per-unit exposure by dividing total reported basement area by the number of apartments in the building. introduces measurement error at the unit level, though the direction of bias is ambiguous. SkadesØkonomi applies equivalent logic for cloudburst apartment damage. We return to the implications of this assumption in the results.

Descriptive statistics are reported in Appendix Tables A1–A4 (permanent residences vs. vacation homes for storm surge; houses vs. apartments for cloudburst). The variation in property characteristics across events provides the within-sample heterogeneity necessary to assess whether performance varies systematically with property and hazard characteristics or is uniformly poor.

6 Results

This section presents the benchmarking results for all three Danish flood damage models across both hazard types. The findings show a clear and consistent pattern: all three models systematically overestimate residential flood damages across events, flood types, and building categories. Predicted damages

exceed observed insurance payouts by large multiples in most cases, COD values are negative throughout, and no model outperforms the naïve baseline of predicting each event’s cost using the historical mean of past payouts. Increased model complexity provides no improvement in predictive performance: SkadesØkonomi, the most elaborate tool, performs comparably to - and sometimes worse than - the simpler models. Sections 6.1 and 6.2 report storm surge results for Oversvømmelsesloven and SkadesØkonomi; Sections 6.3 and 6.4 report urban cloudburst results for Serviceniveaubekendtjørelsen and SkadesØkonomi.

6.1 Oversvømmelsesloven: Storm Surge Events

Oversvømmelsesloven links structural building damage to inundation depth as a fraction of replacement value, and treats content damage as a fixed amount per property type independent of depth. Tables 5–7 report performance metrics for building damage, content damage, and total event costs under both high and low-water level scenarios.

6.1.1 Building damage

Across all four storm surge events and both water level scenarios, Oversvømmelsesloven overestimates structural building damage (Table 5). MAE and RMSE are large relative to observed payouts in every case, indicating that individual event predictions deviate substantially from realized outcomes in absolute terms. COD values are negative for all events under both scenarios, confirming that the model explains less variation in observed losses than the sample mean of past payouts. Thus, the model fails the minimum credibility standard established in Section 4. Prediction errors are particularly pronounced for the January 2017 event under the high-water level scenario (COD of -376.0).

Switching to the low-water level scenario reduces aggregate bias (AD) and improves absolute accuracy metrics (MAE, RMSE) modestly for some events. The Egon event illustrates a pitfall of aggregate evaluation: its AD is relatively small, suggesting total predicted damage is close to the observed total, yet its COD remains negative, revealing that the model distributes damages poorly across individual properties. A model can appear accurate at the aggregate level while being uninformative about where damage occurs—a distinction that matters for spatially targeted adaptation investment.

Table 5: Predictive performance of Oversvømmelsesloven for building damage under high and low-water level scenarios (values in 1,000 DKK, 2023 prices).

Event	Actual Median	Actual SD	Predicted Median	Predicted SD	MAE	RMSE	AD	AAD	COD
High-Water Level									
Bodil	341	491	239	1776	590	1889	116478	79	-13.8
Egon	129	112	168	107	126	166	2055	56	-1.2
Urd	138	196	164	386	255	438	2982	62	-4.1
Jan2017	98	169	239	3233	540	3270	52868	460	-376.0
Low-Water Level									
Bodil	341	491	213	1567	561	1685	26418	18	-11
Egon	129	112	135	86	115	143	518	14	-1
Urd	138	196	157	367	247	419	2445	51	-4
Jan2017	98	169	230	3127	520	3162	49954	434	-351

Note: MAE = Mean Absolute Error; RMSE = Root Mean Squared Error; AD = Absolute Difference; AAD = Average Absolute Difference; COD = coefficient of determination computed out-of-sample. Positive AD indicates overestimation of total damages.

6.1.2 Content damage

Because the model treats content damage as a fixed amount per property type - independent of inundation depth - predicted content losses are identical across both water level scenarios for every event. Thus, the model cannot respond to variation in flood severity. The result (Table 6) is systematic overestimation of residential content damages across all events, with particularly large errors for Bodil and January 2017 and strongly negative COD values throughout. For vacation home content, the model performs somewhat better in relative terms but still exhibits consistent bias and low accuracy. This depth-independence represents a fundamental misspecification, not merely a technical limitation.

Table 6: Predictive performance of Oversvømmelsesloven for content damage (values in 1,000 DKK, 2023 prices).

Event	Actual Median	Actual SD	Predicted Median	Predicted SD	MAE	RMSE	AD	AAD	COD
Residential Goods									
Bodil	12	116	92	651	234	689	107758	172	-34
Egon	0	6	72	21	72	74	718	72	-182
Urd	0	3	127	249	193	306	1934	193	-8965
Jan2017	0	43	93	783	207	804	11272	201	-354
Vacation Home Goods									
Bodil	26	68	15	12	43	73	-23703	28	-0.17
Egon	5	21	13	4	16	21	-12	0	-0.02
Urd	1	25	13	10	19	28	63	2	-0.23
Jan2017	0	9	17	13	18	22	904	15	-5.45

6.1.3 Total event costs and depth sensitivity

The pattern of systematic overestimation observed in the component analyses persists at the aggregate level (Table 7): predicted total damages exceed observed payouts across all events and scenarios, with especially large deviations for January 2017. The lower-water scenario reduces aggregate bias for some events—most notably Bodil—but does not reverse the general pattern of overestimation, and COD values remain negative throughout.

Table 7: Predictive performance of the Oversvømmelsesloven for total event damage under high and low-water level scenarios (values in 1,000 DKK, 2023 prices).

Event	Actual Median	Actual SD	Predicted Median	Predicted SD	MAE	RMSE	AD	AAD	COD
High-Water Level									
Bodil	377	564	275	2212	703	2332	181281	122	-16
Egon	129	120	183	135	144	197	2719	73	-2
Urd	139	213	194	516	302	570	4796	100	-6
Jan2017	104	190	285	3784	643	3830	64803	564	-408
Low-Water Level									
Bodil	377	564	250	2002	673	2127	91221	62	-13
Egon	129	120	149	114	134	171	1182	32	-1
Urd	139	213	188	496	295	551	4258	89	-6
Jan2017	104	190	273	3678	623	3722	61890	538	-385

Note: Total event damage is the sum of building and content damage predictions across all affected properties. Positive AD indicates systematic overestimation.

Figure 1 assesses how sensitive the aggregate damage estimate is to assumed flood height.

For each storm event, the curve shows the ratio of calculated damage to observed insurance payout as a function of an imposed uniform still-water flood level (m). Calculated damage is obtained by applying the Oversvømmelsesloven depth–damage function to every exposed property (ground elevation below 2 m) and summing across the portfolio; the observed payout in the denominator is fixed per event. The dashed line marks parity (ratio = 1), where modelled and observed aggregate losses coincide.

Holding each event’s exposed property set and its observed aggregate payout fixed, we sweep a uniform still-water flood level from 0 to 2.3 m and plot the ratio of modelled to observed aggregate damage. Three features stand out. First, the ratio exceeds one across the entire range of plausible depth values for all events, confirming that overestimation is structural rather than an artifact of a particular depth assumption. Second, the ratio rises monotonically with depth for all events, indicating that the model’s tendency to overestimate becomes more severe at higher inundation levels. For the January 2017 event, the ratio increases from approximately five at low depths to nearly eight at 2.2 m, so overestimation worsens precisely in the high-water conditions used to appraise

major coastal protection investments. Third, each event curve has a unique slope, so a depth assumption that yields an accurate aggregate estimate for one event may be substantially biased for another.

Figure 1: Sensitivity of aggregate modelled damage (Oversvømmelsesloven) to assumed flood height.

6.2 SkadesØkonomi: Storm Surge Events

SkadesØkonomi employs a logarithmic depth–damage specification that implying diminishing marginal damage at higher inundation depths, in contrast to the Oversvømmelsesloven’s linear-fraction approach. Tables 8–10 report results for residential properties, vacation homes, and total damages under both water level scenarios.

6.2.1 Residential properties

For residential buildings, SkadesØkonomi overestimates observed damages across all events and both water level scenarios, with particularly large deviations for Egon and January 2017 under the high-water assumption (Table 8). While switching to the low-water scenario reduces aggregate bias for Bodil, MAE remains high and COD values are negative throughout. The logarithmic specification yields no systematic improvement over Oversvømmelsesloven’s linear approach: both models fail the COD threshold for all events, with identical direction of bias. This is an important negative result. Greater functional form

sophistication, without empirical calibration, does not improve accuracy in this setting.

Table 8: Predictive performance of SkadesØkonomi for residential building damage from coastal flooding (values in 1,000 DKK, 2023 prices).

Event	Actual Median	Actual SD	Predicted Median	Predicted SD	MAE	RMSE	AD	AAD	COD
High-Water Level									
Bodil	387	725	883	381	661	860	210578	335	-0.4
Egon	53	185	1163	283	940	984	9405	940	-30.4
Urd	109	193	601	570	650	782	4633	463	-17.3
Jan2017	50	221	842	618	715	883	33808	604	-15.2
Low-Water Level									
Bodil	387	725	660	446	589	807	46428	74	-0.2
Egon	53	185	693	337	547	607	4941	494	-11.0
Urd	109	193	506	569	588	716	3563	356	-14.3
Jan2017	50	221	744	593	669	817	29704	530	-12.9

6.2.2 Vacation Homes

For vacation homes, prediction errors vary more substantially across events and models than for permanent residences (Table 9). Bodil under the high-water scenario is the only event and scenario combination in the entire storm surge analysis to yield a positive COD (0.02), a value too close to zero to indicate a meaningful predictive power. All other cases show substantial over- or underprediction with large MAE values and negative COD. The variability across events for this building category likely reflects the geographic concentration of vacation homes in coastal areas that differ in topography and exposure characteristics from the settings in which the model’s parameters were specified, compounding the depth measurement uncertainty discussed in Section 5.3.

Table 9: Predictive performance of SkadesØkonomi for vacation home damage from coastal flooding (values in 1,000 DKK, 2023 prices).

Event	Actual Median	Actual SD	Predicted Median	Predicted SD	MAE	RMSE	AD	AAD	COD
High-Water Level									
Bodil	373	397	315	131	273	394	-108202	127	0.01
Egon	166	86	320	87	156	198	4091	152	-4.52
Urd	158	220	214	129	175	245	216	6	-0.28
Jan2017	162	151	247	160	145	197	2473	42	-0.73
Low-Water Level									
Bodil	373	397	258	170	307	438	-180707	211	-0.2
Egon	166	86	188	217	218	263	-3125	116	-8.8
Urd	158	220	189	145	177	248	-985	26	-0.3
Jan2017	162	151	225	166	142	205	474	8	-0.9

6.2.3 Total event costs and depth sensitivity

Aggregating across property types, SkadesØkonomi consistently overestimates total storm surge damages (Table 10). MAE exceeds DKK 300,000 for Egon and January 2017 under the high-water scenario, and COD values remain negative across the board. Figure 2 plots the predicted-to-observed damage ratio against water depth. The logarithmic damage function produces negligible or even underestimated payouts at low depths, followed by a steep rise into severe overestimation beyond a threshold (near 120 cm above DVR90 for January 2017, where predicted damages exceed observed payouts by a factor of four or more). The model is thus most biased precisely at the high-water levels used in appraisals of major coastal protection. Figure 2 also reveals that, for some events, there exists a narrow depth range at which the model’s predictions are close to observed outcomes (illustrated where event curves cross the parity line). This reflects the continuous depth function rather than calibration and provides no guidance on which depth to assume in practice.

Table 10: Predictive performance of SkadesØkonomi for total damage from coastal flooding (values in 1,000 DKK, 2023 prices).

Event	Actual Median	Actual SD	Predicted Median	Predicted SD	MAE	RMSE	AD	AAD	COD
High-Water Level									
Bodil	377	564	449	403	437	634	102376	69	-0.3
Egon	129	120	358	369	368	539	13496	365	-19.7
Urd	139	213	222	321	274	418	4850	101	-2.9
Jan2017	104	190	299	510	422	632	36281	315	-10.1
Low-Water Level									
Bodil	377	564	341	383	426	622	-134279	91	-0.13
Egon	129	120	233	354	307	388	1816	49	-9.72
Urd	139	213	194	311	263	394	2578	54	-2.37
Jan2017	104	190	273	487	399	589	30178	262	-8.95

6.3 Property-level predictive accuracy

The preceding results evaluate model performance at the aggregate event level and by building category. To assess whether the models also provide reliable predictions for individual affected properties, Figure 3 compares observed insurance payouts with property-level damages predicted by SkadesØkonomi and Oversvømmelsesloven for the four storm surge events: Bodil, Egon, Urd, and the January 2017 storm. The horizontal axis shows observed insurance payouts, while the vertical axis shows model-predicted damages; both are shown on logarithmic scales. The dashed 45-degree line indicates perfect prediction.

The figure shows substantial dispersion around the 45-degree line, indicating limited predictive accuracy at the individual-property level. SkadesØkonomi predictions cluster somewhat more closely around observed payouts, whereas

Figure 2: Ratio of predicted to observed residential damage as a function of assumed flood height — SkadesØkonomi

Oversvømmelsesloven displays wider dispersion and more frequent extreme over-predictions, particularly for Bodil and the January 2017 storm. For both models, many observations lie above the 45-degree line, indicating a tendency to over-estimate realized insurance payouts. This pattern is especially pronounced for properties with relatively low observed damages, where predicted losses often exceed actual compensation by several orders of magnitude. These results are consistent with the negative out-of-sample COD values reported above and show that poor aggregate predictive performance is mirrored by substantial property-level prediction errors.

Figure 3: Property-Level Comparison of Predicted and Actual Insurance Payouts for the SkadesØkonomi and Oversvømmelsesloven Flood Damage Models

6.4 Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen: Cloudburst Events

Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen is the principal tool for cloudburst damage assessment in Danish municipal planning. Its linear area-based specification distinguishes between above-ground living area and basement flooding and applies standardized unit damage values to each. The model covers single-family houses and row houses but not apartment buildings. For multi-unit dwellings, the model assumes that only basement flooding occurs, so predicted apartment damage depends entirely on the approximated per-unit basement area. Tables 11–13 report results for houses, apartments, and total event costs respectively.

6.4.1 Houses

For single-family houses and row houses, the model systematically and substantially overestimates observed insurance payouts across all cloudburst events (Table 11). MAE and RMSE values are large, and COD is negative for every event. Overestimation is present for both the dominant July 2011 Copenhagen cloudburst and smaller, localized events, suggesting that the model’s unit damage values (whose derivation is undocumented as noted in Section 3.2) reflect potential physical damage well above the compensated losses that materialize in practice.

Table 11: Predictive performance of Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen for flooded houses during cloudburst events (values in 1,000 DKK, 2023 prices).

Event	Actual Median	Actual SD	Predicted Median	Predicted SD	MAE	RMSE	AD	AAD	COD
14-08-2010	43	203	216	79	186	246	506114	126	-0.5
02-07-2011	59	154	200	70	154	191	1068748	100	-0.6
14-08-2011	26	83	196	78	176	198	19688	164	-4.7
26-08-2011	26	85	197	62	160	176	50793	148	-3.3
29-06-2012	18	37	193	56	163	174	14060	163	-21.7
06-08-2012	40	77	206	53	157	173	40531	147	-4.1
26-08-2013	29	131	206	60	165	198	41785	148	-1.3
23-05-2014	19	108	191	56	164	190	94679	146	-2.1
30-08-2014	28	78	226	92	196	219	122622	189	-6.8
16-10-2014	28	218	189	56	180	244	18076	103	-0.3

6.4.2 Apartments

For apartments, the model substantially overpredicts across all events (Table 12). Observed median damages range from 7,000 to 19,000 DKK, whereas predicted median damages range from 85,000 to 145,000 DKK. This systematic overprediction is reflected in the large MAE and RMSE. AAD are also high indicating considerable discrepancies between predicted and observed damages at the property level. COD is negative for all events, ranging from -3 to -208 . Model performance is particularly poor for the 14 August 2011 and 26 August 2011 events.

Table 12: Predictive performance of Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen for flooded apartments during cloudburst events (values in 1,000 DKK, 2023 prices).

Event	Actual Median	Actual SD	Predicted Median	Predicted SD	MAE	RMSE	AD	AAD	COD
14-08-2010	13	60	122	54	111	125	148370	100	-3
02-07-2011	14	66	118	54	107	125	1216278	96	-3
14-08-2011	13	12	145	59	108	123	753	108	-128
26-08-2011	10	9	134	44	123	131	3949	123	-208
29-06-2012	19	32	107	23	86	91	1599	84	-8
06-08-2012	9	41	107	51	100	111	11655	94	-6
26-08-2013	7	44	85	36	77	84	1609	73	-3
23-05-2014	12	40	101	40	90	100	6343	86	-5
30-08-2014	13	51	124	59	118	134	163502	112	-6
16-10-2014	11	27	126	47	116	128	1860	116	-24

6.4.3 Total event costs

Aggregating houses and apartments, the model consistently overestimates aggregate damages, with predicted medians ranging from 157,000 to 190,000 DKK, against observed medians of only 14,000 to 29,000 DKK. This overestimation is reflected in the large MAE and RMSE. AAD are also substantial indicating that predicted damages are frequently more than double the observed values. COD is negative for all events, ranging from -0.3 to -18.8 . The weakest performance is observed for the 29 June 2012 event, which exhibits the most negative COD value despite relatively moderate absolute prediction errors, suggesting that the model fails to capture the limited variation in observed damages.

Table 13: Total event cost predictions of Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen versus observed insurance payouts (values in 1,000 DKK, 2023 prices).

Event	Actual Median	Actual SD	Predicted Median	Predicted SD	MAE	RMSE	AD	AAD	COD
14-08-2010	29	180	185	83	163	219	774073	116	-0.5
02-07-2011	24	119	157	72	129	157	2705812	99	-0.8
14-08-2011	23	82	189	80	169	190	21424	154	-4.4
26-08-2011	23	87	183	66	153	171	59187	139	-2.9
29-06-2012	14	35	164	62	141	154	18558	141	-18.8
06-08-2012	25	69	180	69	139	156	56303	131	-4.2
26-08-2013	23	117	190	67	151	181	50943	136	-1.4
23-05-2014	17	98	180	61	153	178	114243	139	-2.3
30-08-2014	16	61	160	86	147	169	345781	142	-6.7
16-10-2014	25	196	172	58	164	223	23102	104	-0.3

6.5 SkadesØkonomi: Cloudburst Events

SkadesØkonomi applies the same area-based framework as Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen for cloudburst events but extends it to vacation homes and adds

a garage damage term, giving it more parameters and broader property scope. Tables 14–16 report results for houses, apartments, and total event costs.

6.5.1 Houses

For single-family houses, SkadesØkonomi replicates the pattern observed for Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen: systematic overestimation across all events, with particularly large absolute errors for smaller-scale events where the predicted-to-observed ratio is highest (Table 14). COD values are negative throughout, and the magnitude of prediction errors is comparable to those produced by the simpler regulatory model despite SkadesØkonomi’s greater complexity. This convergence of performance across models with different functional forms and parameter sets reinforces a central finding of the international validation literature: when damage functions are not calibrated against observed losses, additional model complexity does not improve predictive accuracy and may simply amplify the consequences of miscalibrated inputs.

Table 14: Predictive performance of SkadesØkonomi for houses during cloud-burst events (values in 1,000 DKK, 2023 prices).

Event	Actual Median	Actual SD	Predicted Median	Predicted SD	MAE	RMSE	AD	AAD	COD
14-08-2010	43	203	216	79	186	246	506114	126	-0.5
02-07-2011	59	154	200	70	154	191	1068748	100	-0.6
14-08-2011	26	83	196	78	176	198	19688	164	-4.7
26-08-2011	26	85	197	62	160	176	50793	148	-3.3
29-06-2012	18	37	193	56	163	174	14060	163	-21.7
06-08-2012	40	77	206	53	157	173	40531	147	-4.1
26-08-2013	29	131	206	60	165	198	41785	148	-1.3
23-05-2014	19	108	191	56	164	190	94679	146	-2.1
30-08-2014	28	78	226	92	196	219	122622	189	-6.8
16-10-2014	28	218	189	56	180	244	18076	103	-0.3

6.5.2 Apartments

For apartments SkadesØkonomi behaves different from Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen (Table 15): predicted median damages equal to zero for nine of the ten events and only 20,000 DKK for the 14 August 2011 event. So, the model generally underpredicts observed damages, whose median values range from 7,000 to 19,000 DKK. Despite this tendency to underestimate losses, SkadesØkonomi exhibits considerably lower prediction errors (see MAE and RMSE for details) than Serviceniveaubekendtgørelsen. AAD are also substantially lower, indicating a closer correspondence between predicted and observed damages. Nevertheless, COD remains negative for all events, ranging from -0.09 to -5.02 . The poorest performance is observed for the 14 August 2011 event.

Table 15: Predictive performance of SkadesØkonomi for apartments during cloudburst events (values in 1,000 DKK, 2023 prices).

Event	Actual Median	Actual SD	Predicted Median	Predicted SD	MAE	RMSE	AD	AAD	COD
14-08-2010	13	60	0	14	31	65	-36866	25	-0.14
02-07-2011	14	66	0	12	30	70	-326034	26	-0.11
14-08-2011	13	12	20	21	19	27	39	6	-5.02
26-08-2011	10	9	0	17	15	20	-3	0	-2.97
29-06-2012	19	32	0	14	20	36	-279	15	-0.29
06-08-2012	9	41	0	11	23	46	-2139	17	-0.21
26-08-2013	7	44	0	8	21	48	-374	17	-0.73
23-05-2014	12	40	0	13	23	43	-1222	17	-0.12
30-08-2014	13	51	0	13	22	54	-25175	17	-0.09
16-10-2014	11	27	0	19	21	35	-168	11	-0.85

6.5.3 Total event costs

For total event costs (Table 16), the model substantially overpredicts aggregate damages for nine of the ten events. The sole exception is the 30 August 2014 event, for which the predicted median is slightly below the observed value. This systematic overestimation is reflected in the large MAE and RMSE. AAD are likewise substantial, indicating large discrepancies between predicted and observed event-level damages. COD is negative for all events, ranging from -0.3 to -17.9 . The poorest performance is observed for the 29 June 2012 event, which exhibits the most negative COD value despite not having the largest absolute prediction error, suggesting that the model fails to capture the relatively limited variation in observed damages for that event.

Table 16: Total event cost predictions of SkadesØkonomi versus observed insurance payouts, cloudburst events (values in 1,000 DKK, 2023 prices).

Event	Actual Median	Actual SD	Predicted Median	Predicted SD	MAE	RMSE	AD	AAD	COD
14-08-2010	29	180	180	113	145	213	588768	88	-0.4
02-07-2011	24	119	117	109	93	141	1161476	43	-0.4
14-08-2011	23	82	188	87	165	188	20710	149	-4.3
26-08-2011	23	87	180	80	145	167	55235	130	-2.7
29-06-2012	14	35	164	83	131	150	16583	126	-17.9
06-08-2012	25	69	173	104	117	146	42509	99	-3.6
26-08-2013	23	117	190	77	147	181	48905	131	-1.4
23-05-2014	17	98	179	77	147	176	106611	130	-2.2
30-08-2014	16	61	14	125	90	140	156981	64	-4.3
16-10-2014	25	196	170	72	158	220	21073	94	-0.3

7 Discussion

The results show a clear and consistent pattern: the three Danish flood damage models systematically overestimate residential losses, fail to explain variation in realized payouts across the events examined, and perform worse than the historical mean as a predictor of event-level costs. This section interprets those findings on three levels: the economic consequences for cost–benefit appraisal; why the validation gap persists; and the generalizability of the Danish evidence.

7.1 Economic Consequences of Systematic Overestimation

The primary economic consequence of the overestimation documented here is the inflation of the apparent benefits of flood protection investment. In a standard CBA, the benefit of a protective measure is the expected annual damage it avoids, integrated across the probability distribution of flood events and discounted over the investment horizon. When damage estimates are systematically too high, the computed benefit stream is inflated correspondingly. At the magnitudes observed here - predicted damages, in most cases, exceeding observed payouts by factors of two to five or more across events - the distortion is not marginal. Benefit–cost ratios derived from these models may clear investment thresholds that would not be reached under well-calibrated damage estimates, directing public resources toward protection measures whose true social returns are substantially lower than appraised. This represents a form of systematic misallocation that is difficult to detect precisely because the models that produce it are officially endorsed and their outputs are rarely benchmarked against realized losses.

Danish municipalities and national authorities use these models not only to evaluate individual projects but also to prioritize among competing adaptation strategies, e.g. hard coastal defense, green infrastructure, property-level measures, or managed retreat. If all benefit streams are overestimated by comparable factors, their ranking may be preserved despite inflated absolute figures. However, where different strategies draw on different model components, e.g. coastal protection on the storm surge module while urban drainage on the cloudburst module), the relative overestimation need not be uniform, and rankings may be distorted even if a uniform scaling correction is applied. This possibility cannot be resolved without component-level validation of the kind provided in this paper, which reveals that performance varies substantially across models, hazard types, and property categories.

There is also a distributional dimension. Flood protection investment decisions determine which communities receive protection, at what standard, and at whose expense. In the Danish context, this financing question differs across hazards. Cloudburst adaptation is typically financed through municipalities and private utility companies responsible for wastewater and drainage infrastructure, implying a relatively collective financing model within the municipality and among utility consumers. Storm surge protection, by contrast, is generally intended to be financed by households and firms in proportion to the benefits

they receive, although municipal practice varies considerably in how this principle is interpreted and implemented (Fryd, Panduro, Horn-Petersen, Vejre, & Anker, 2021). Model error therefore has distributional consequences not only for where protection is prioritized, but also for how adaptation costs are allocated. When damage estimates overstate losses in some areas more than others - for example because models poorly represent apartment buildings in dense urban settings - the resulting investment priorities and cost-sharing arrangements may reflect the geography of model error as much as the geography of actual flood risk.

7.2 Precision Without Accuracy: The Information Economics of Flood Damage Models

Increased model complexity provides no systematic improvement in predictive accuracy: SkadesØkonomi, the most methodologically elaborate of the three tools, performs no better than the simpler regulatory models in the empirical comparison presented above. This has a clear interpretation in the economics of information: in the absence of empirical calibration against realized losses, additional parameters and more elaborate functional forms amplify the consequences of miscalibrated inputs rather than attenuating them. The deeper problem, however, is not merely that the models are imprecise but that their lack of transparency prevents users and decision-makers from assessing the extent of this imprecision. None of the three models discloses uncertainty ranges that reflect its true predictive variance; cost-benefit analyses built on their outputs do not report the possibility that the benefit stream is overstated by a factor of two to five. Under these conditions, model users - municipal planners, national authorities, and the analysts who advise them - are operating with systematically misleading information about the reliability of the inputs to their decisions. As Pindyck (2017) argues, precise looking but poorly calibrated estimates can be more misleading than transparent acknowledgment of uncertainty, precisely because they discourage the scrutiny that would reveal their limitations.

7.3 Why the Validation Gap Persists: Institutional Incentives and Model Governance

The absence of empirical validation for the Danish models reflects structural features of damage model development and governance rather than incidental oversight. Three features are particularly important. First, model development is driven by regulatory demand for deployable decision tools, not by scientific standards for validation: the commissioning structure rewards timely delivery, not empirical testing, and validation - when it occurs - is typically conducted by the model developer using the same data and assumptions that informed construction. Second, once embedded in regulatory frameworks, models acquire institutional inertia: revising official damage functions requires revisiting the analyses that underpinned prior investment commitments and may entail

acknowledging that those commitments rested on unreliable information - a political economy that favors preservation over correction. Third, the validation gap is compounded dynamically by climate change. Depth–damage functions calibrated to historical exposure conditions may become progressively unreliable as sea levels rise, precipitation extremes intensify, and the building stock adapts in ways that alter vulnerability at any given inundation depth (Merz et al., 2015). The current Danish framework, in which models are developed once and applied indefinitely without systematic review, contains no mechanism for detecting or correcting this performance drift over time.

Critically, the persistence of the validation gap is not primarily a data problem. The Danish insurance infrastructure - the mandatory Stormrådet pool for storm surges and comprehensive private cloudburst records - provides a validation benchmark of exceptional quality that has not been systematically used. Similarly, large insurance datasets in the United States have been shown, when properly analyzed, to yield robust empirical estimates that diverge substantially from HAZUS-MH (Porter et al., 2023; Wing et al., 2020). The validation gap reflects the absence of institutional requirements for validation rather than the absence of suitable data.

7.4 Generalizability and Policy Implications

The characteristics that explain poor model performance in Denmark - undocumented parameter derivation, synthetic or semi-empirical damage functions, and the absence of prior validation - are shared by the majority of residential flood damage models in international use, as the review in Section 2 demonstrates. Where independent validation studies have been conducted internationally, they find systematic bias and poor explanatory power of the kind documented here: studies of German depth–damage functions show poor fit when confronted with household-level data (Kreibich et al., 2010; Schröter et al., 2014); comparative European analyses reveal order-of-magnitude variation in model predictions for identical events (Jongman et al., 2012); Dutch validation exercises document systematic over- and underestimation across property categories (D. J. Wagenaar et al., 2016). Denmark is distinctive not because its models perform unusually poor, but because its insurance data makes it possible to document the problem rigorously. The findings reported here are therefore best interpreted as evidence of a general structural problem that becomes visible when suitable validation data, like the Danish, are available.

Three governance reforms follow from this diagnosis. First, empirical validation against realized losses should become a routine component of the development and updating of official flood damage models, rather than an exceptional exercise. Second, model documentation should meet minimum transparency standards: the derivation of damage parameters, their empirical basis, and the results of any validation exercise should be disclosed in a form that permits external scrutiny. Third, model outputs used in cost–benefit analysis should be accompanied by uncertainty ranges that reflect empirical predictive performance—not merely sensitivity to input assumptions within the model’s

own logic. An uncertainty range that ignores the model’s systematic tendency to overestimate realized losses by large multiples provides a false sense of robustness in the underlying analysis. More broadly, regulatory frameworks should require that models meet validation standards as a condition of official endorsement - standards that most internationally used tools would currently fail.

8 Conclusions

This paper has provided the first systematic empirical benchmarking of the three official Danish flood damage models against realized insurance payouts from major storm surge and cloudburst events between 2010 and 2017. The results are consistent across all three models, both hazard types, and all property categories: predicted damages exceed observed payouts by factors of two to five or more; COD values are negative throughout, confirming that the historical mean of past payouts outperforms official damage functions as a predictor of event costs; and increased model complexity provides no improvement in predictive accuracy. These findings have direct consequences for cost–benefit appraisal: when damage estimates overstate realized losses by the magnitudes we document, computed benefit streams are inflated correspondingly, and investment decisions may misallocate adaptation resources. Cost–benefit analysis may then lend unwarranted confidence to quantitative inputs whose relationship to expected realized losses is empirically unestablished. The precision of model outputs is an artifact of deterministic model structure, not a reflection of informational content.

The Danish evidence points to a structural validation gap that extends beyond the national context. The characteristics associated with poor performance here—undocumented parameter derivation, absence of empirical validation, and no disclosure of predictive uncertainty—are shared by many residential flood damage models in international use, including HAZUS-MH, the Rhine Atlas, and the JRC global model. Denmark provides an unusually strong empirical test case because its mandatory storm surge insurance pool and comprehensive cloudburst records allow model performance to be measured systematically against realized losses. The findings reported here therefore indicate a general structural problem in flood damage modelling rather than a country-specific shortcoming.

Three limitations warrant acknowledgment. The study is retrospective, covering 2010–2017, and cannot address whether model performance has changed since then or how it will evolve as climate change alters flood frequency and intensity. The minimum claims threshold applied to storm surge events may introduce a selection bias toward more severe events. And the insurance benchmark captures compensated losses rather than total economic damages, though this does not materially affect the comparison given that the Danish models are designed to estimate precisely the scope of loss the insurance data record.

The study points toward three priorities. At the research level, routine empirical validation of flood damage models against insurance payout data and loss

registries should become a standard scientific practice rather than an exceptional exercise. At the modelling level, the results reinforce the case for a reorientation toward transparent, empirically calibrated approaches of the kind exemplified by BN-FLEMOps: models whose parameters are estimated from observed losses, whose uncertainty is explicitly represented, and whose predictive performance is tested out-of-sample before institutional deployment. At the governance level, regulatory frameworks that rely on model-based damage estimates for investment appraisal should require minimum standards of transparency and empirical validation as a condition of official endorsement—standards that none of the three Danish models, and few of their international counterparts, currently meets. Ensuring the empirical credibility of damage estimates is not a technical refinement at the margin of climate adaptation policy: it is a precondition for that policy to allocate resources efficiently and communicate risk honestly.

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9 Appendix

Event	Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Q25	Q75
Bodil	Size	99.9	53.24	21	485	62	130
Bodil	Size_houses	140.71	54.02	36	485	102	164
Bodil	Size_vacationhomes	69.54	24.76	21	176	52	82
Bodil	Elevation	1.42	0.31	-0.51	1.99	1.3	1.63
Bodil	Elevation_houses	1.49	0.29	0	1.99	1.36	1.65
Bodil	Elevation_vacationhomes	1.36	0.32	-0.51	1.99	1.23	1.55
Bodil	Building_value	1825103.78	6292275.2	0	66447109	472282	1355656
Egon	Size	90.76	44.42	40	189	60	114
Egon	Size_houses	148.1	41.16	60	189	131.5	177.5
Egon	Size_vacationhomes	69.52	20.32	40	128	56	80
Egon	Elevation	1.6	0.25	1.15	1.91	1.4	1.87
Egon	Elevation_houses	1.55	0.18	1.27	1.91	1.41	1.64
Egon	Elevation_vacationhomes	1.61	0.27	1.15	1.87	1.4	1.87
Egon	Building_value	650517.68	329775.16	322420	1588738	408421	774009
Urd	Size	82.98	59.73	23	343	50.75	88
Urd	Size_houses	159.64	85	74	343	104.5	170.5
Urd	Size_vacationhomes	61.36	22.78	23	129	48.5	70.5
Urd	Elevation	1.36	0.2	0.9	1.99	1.27	1.4
Urd	Elevation_houses	1.48	0.27	1.19	1.99	1.27	1.65
Urd	Elevation_vacationhomes	1.33	0.17	0.9	1.9	1.27	1.37
Urd	Building_value	1060413.28	1824848.79	242983	12562931	348760.25	948820
Jan2017	Size	106.79	67.21	32	418	56	149.75
Jan2017	Size_houses	150.36	62.62	51	418	114.25	171.5
Jan2017	Size_vacationhomes	64.67	38.73	32	308	46.25	69.25
Jan2017	Elevation	1.32	0.32	0	2	1.17	1.47
Jan2017	Elevation_houses	1.38	0.32	0.39	1.98	1.17	1.51
Jan2017	Elevation_vacationhomes	1.27	0.3	0	2	1.19	1.43
Jan2017	Building_value	1882245.65	7902538.52	54627	86453444	544599	1398906.75

Table A1 Storm flood summary statistics (Continuous variables)
Table A2 Storm flood summary statistics (Dummy variables)

Event	N	N_with_garage	N_without_garage	Prop_with
Bodil	1505	55	1450	0.04
Egon	37	0	37	0
Urd	50	1	49	0.02
Jan2017	118	3	115	0.03

Table A3 Cloudburst summary statistics (Continuous variables)

Event	Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Q25	Q75
Event1	Size	135.95	55.08	24.00	399.00	96.00	163.75
Event1	Size_houses	144.39	54.85	24.00	399.00	103.00	172.00
Event1	Size_apartments	99.63	39.00	33.00	380.00	72.00	118.00
Event1	Basement	39.23	44.68	0.00	283.00	0.00	75.00
Event1	Basement_houses	45.31	46.17	0.00	283.00	0.00	81.00
Event1	Basement_apartments	13.06	23.91	0.00	176.92	0.00	19.35
Event2	Size	118.54	46.20	10.00	399.00	86.00	141.00
Event2	Size_houses	133.33	45.05	10.00	399.00	101.00	154.00
Event2	Size_apartments	97.08	38.84	11.00	399.00	71.00	114.00
Event2	Basement	30.93	40.12	0.00	297.00	0.00	61.00
Event2	Basement_houses	44.10	44.69	0.00	297.00	0.00	78.00
Event2	Basement_apartments	11.80	20.73	0.00	193.12	0.00	18.80
Event3	Size	136.37	53.43	28.00	319.00	102.00	155.75
Event3	Size_houses	138.69	52.89	45.00	319.00	103.50	157.00
Event3	Size_apartments	81.14	35.03	28.00	115.00	58.50	105.00
Event3	Basement	39.13	43.39	0.00	173.00	0.00	70.00
Event3	Basement_houses	39.35	43.73	0.00	173.00	0.00	70.50
Event3	Basement_apartments	34.01	36.46	0.00	108.00	10.53	37.19
Event4	Size	135.05	45.30	42.00	346.00	105.00	158.00
Event4	Size_houses	137.84	44.86	42.00	346.00	109.00	160.00
Event4	Size_apartments	97.24	32.86	49.00	178.00	74.00	116.00
Event4	Basement	24.42	41.69	0.00	175.00	0.00	48.00
Event4	Basement_houses	24.96	42.46	0.00	175.00	0.00	49.75
Event4	Basement_apartments	17.10	28.70	0.00	90.00	0.00	38.67
Event5	Size	115.45	42.06	28.00	314.00	86.00	142.00
Event5	Size_houses	120.15	42.07	28.00	314.00	92.00	148.50
Event5	Size_apartments	78.76	16.05	45.00	117.00	69.00	85.00
Event5	Basement	26.55	37.51	0.00	164.00	0.00	53.00
Event5	Basement_houses	28.04	38.68	0.00	164.00	0.00	54.75
Event5	Basement_apartments	14.87	24.29	0.00	81.00	0.00	30.50
Event6	Size	126.43	47.66	14.00	295.00	92.00	155.00
Event6	Size_houses	140.91	43.51	32.00	295.00	110.00	164.00
Event6	Size_apartments	89.24	36.48	14.00	253.00	66.75	103.25
Event6	Basement	36.94	42.40	0.00	169.00	0.00	71.01
Event6	Basement_houses	47.65	44.32	0.00	169.00	0.00	83.00
Event6	Basement_apartments	9.42	17.94	0.00	72.38	0.00	13.72
Event7	Size	131.86	44.99	35.00	395.00	98.00	157.75
Event7	Size_houses	135.02	43.56	43.00	395.00	100.50	160.00
Event7	Size_apartments	70.04	22.70	35.00	121.00	51.50	84.50
Event7	Basement	39.41	43.18	0.00	260.00	0.00	70.75
Event7	Basement_houses	41.10	43.50	0.00	260.00	0.00	72.00
Event7	Basement_apartments	6.32	13.31	0.00	52.80	0.00	4.65
Event8	Size	129.01	42.37	12.00	392.00	102.00	153.00
Event8	Size_houses	133.37	40.55	22.00	392.00	107.00	155.00
Event8	Size_apartments	83.01	33.01	12.00	273.00	62.50	94.00
Event8	Basement	28.82	40.17	0.00	273.00	0.00	60.00

Event	Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Q25	Q75
Event8	Basement_houses	30.43	41.13	0.00	273.00	0.00	64.00
Event8	Basement_apartments	11.85	21.88	0.00	147.74	0.00	23.04
Event9	Size	127.54	55.77	11.00	397.00	86.00	154.50
Event9	Size_houses	156.63	55.34	24.00	397.00	122.00	180.00
Event9	Size_apartments	102.15	42.06	11.00	374.00	73.00	121.00
Event9	Basement	31.90	41.35	0.00	286.00	0.00	56.54
Event9	Basement_houses	53.62	47.22	0.00	286.00	0.00	85.00
Event9	Basement_apartments	12.94	22.05	0.00	193.12	0.00	19.91
Event10	Size	128.46	45.30	47.00	278.00	91.00	156.50
Event10	Size_houses	130.83	45.32	47.00	278.00	91.00	160.00
Event10	Size_apartments	95.35	30.06	53.00	177.00	73.75	115.25
Event10	Basement	27.57	36.62	0.00	142.00	0.00	58.67
Event10	Basement_houses	28.16	36.94	0.00	142.00	0.00	60.00
Event10	Basement_apartments	19.36	31.57	0.00	128.00	0.00	31.80

Table A4 Cloudburst summary statistics (Dummy variables)

Event	N	N_with_garage	N_without_garage	Prop_with
Event1	8950	229	8721	0.03
Event2	33835	406	33429	0.01
Event3	174	3	171	0.02
Event4	539	16	523	0.03
Event5	185	5	180	0.03
Event6	514	15	499	0.03
Event7	474	14	460	0.03
Event8	1040	35	1005	0.03
Event9	3279	36	3243	0.01
Event10	299	10	289	0.03